

Synthesis and spectral characterization of calcium(II), cobalt(II) and copper(II) complexes derived from Schiff base of cephalixin

B. Thirumagal^{a*}, Suman Malik^a, Bharati Jain^b and S. A. Iqbal^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Sadhuvasvani College, Bairagarh, Bhopal-462 030, Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : thirumagalbl@gmail.com

^bDepartment of Chemistry, SNGG PG College, Shivaji Nagar, Bhopal-462 016, Madhya Pradesh, India

^cDepartment of Chemistry, Saifia Science College, Bhopal-462 011, Madhya Pradesh, India

Manuscript received 22 September 2009, revised 08 June 2010, accepted 18 August 2010

Abstract : The metal complexes of Ca^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II} with Schiff base of cephalixin (salicylidene cephalixin) of the type ML₂ (where M = Ca^{II}, Co^{II} or Cu^{II} and L = Schiff base of cephalixin) have been prepared via Schiff base, obtained by the condensation of cephalixin with salicylaldehyde. They form 2 : 1 ligand to metal complexes with Ca^{II}, Co^{II} and Cu^{II}, as indicated by conductometric titrations. The complexes have been characterized by various physico-chemical techniques such as elemental analysis, molar conductance and spectral analysis such as mass, UV and IR.

Keywords : Cephalixin, Schiff base, complexes, conductometry, spectra.

Introduction

The presence of a lone pair of electrons in a sp² hybridized orbital of nitrogen atom of the azomethine group is of considerable chemical and biological importance^{1,2}. Because of the relative easiness of preparation, synthetic flexibility, and the special property of C=N group, Schiff bases are generally excellent chelating agents^{3,4} especially when a functional group like -OH or -SH is present close to the azomethine group so as to form a five or six membered ring with the metal ion. Many drugs possess modified toxicological and pharmacological properties when they are complexed⁵⁻⁷ with metal.

The most widely studied metals are copper(II) and zinc(II) which were proved beneficial in diseases such as tuberculosis, cancers⁸⁻¹⁰ etc. Schiff base (salen type) complexes of calcium have also been synthesized and characterized^{11,12}. Cephalixin belongs to the first generation cephalosporins and resistance to it may be related to the extensive use of these drugs causing resistance to cephalosporins¹³⁻¹⁵. This work involves the synthesis and characterization of some metal complexes of Schiff base (SACELX) derived from cephalixin (CELX).

Results and discussion

The condensation of cephalixin with salicylaldehyde

results in the formation of salicylidene cephalixin (Schiff base)¹⁶. The complexes were synthesized by reacting Schiff base ligand with metal ions in the ratio 2 : 1 in the methanolic medium. The complexes do not melt on heating but decompose at high temperatures. They are sparingly soluble in water, methanol, ethanol and acetone. However they are soluble in hot methanol. The physico-chemical data of Schiff base and their complexes were studied and are listed in Table 1.

Conductance measurements :

The conductivity of these complexes in 10⁻³ M methanolic solution are very low in the range of 6.5 × 10⁻⁵ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹ dm⁻³ to 7.9 × 10⁻⁵ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹ dm⁻³, revealing their non-electrolytic nature.

IR spectra :

The IR spectra of Schiff base ligand and its complexes were recorded in KBr pellets in the 4000-400 cm⁻¹ range with a Spectrum BX Series spectrophotometer and compared^{17,18}. Some important characteristic IR frequencies of Schiff base ligand and its complexes are recorded in Table 2.

The spectra showed most of the absorption bands of ligand and some new bands due to the coordination of

Table 1. Physico-chemical characteristics of Schiff base and its metal complexes

Compd./ Mol. formula/ Mol. weight	Colour and decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Molar conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
			C	H	N	S	M	
Salicylidene cephalexin (Schiff base)/ $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}/$ 451	Yellowish orange 192	79	59.04 (61.19)	5.43 (4.65)	8.99 (9.31)	6.08 (7.09)		36.8
Salicylidene cephalexin- Ca^{II} complex/ $\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{10}\text{S}_2\text{Ca}/$ 976	Orange red 205	74	55.12 (56.56)	3.81 (4.09)	8.24 (8.61)	6.22 (6.56)	4.00 (4.09)	13.6
Salicylidene cephalexin- Co^{II} complex/ $\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{10}\text{S}_2\text{Co}/$ 995	Light brown 289	74	54.71 (55.48)	3.72 (4.02)	7.92 (8.44)	5.96 (6.43)	5.52 (5.72)	12.5
Salicylidene cephalexin- Cu^{II} complex/ $\text{C}_{46}\text{H}_{40}\text{N}_6\text{O}_{10}\text{S}_2\text{Cu}/$ 963	Dark brown 290		54.82 (55.22)	3.11 (4.00)	8.24 (8.40)	6.22 (6.40)	6.13 (6.36)	16.4

Table 2. Principal IR spectral data of the CELX, SACE LX and its complexes

Assignments for	Cephalexin (cm^{-1})	Salicylidene cephalexin (cm^{-1})	Salicylidene cephalexin- Ca^{II} complex (cm^{-1})	Salicylidene cephalexin- Co^{II} complex (cm^{-1})	Salicylidene cephalexin- Cu^{II} complex (cm^{-1})
Free NH_2	3500	-	-	-	-
-CH=N-	-	1674	1672	1635	1628
OH	-	3242	-	-	-
C-O (phenolic)	-	1277	1335	1330	1335
Aldehydic C-H stretching attached to benzene ring	-	2770	2800	2780	2779
M-N	-	-	490	498	494
M-O	-	-	701	699	698
Chelation	-	-	1384	1374	1379
Coordinated water	-	-	3395	3324	3322

ligands with metal ions with N and O as donors. The spectra of the Schiff base ligand showed a broad vibration band at 3242 cm^{-1} . This can be assigned to phenolic

OH group of the salicylaldehydic moiety. The disappearance of this peak in the spectra of complexes derived from Schiff base of cephalexin indicates the deprotonation

of phenolic proton of salicylaldehydic moiety prior to coordination^{19,20}. The band assigned to the azomethine group in the free Schiff base ligand of cephalexin (SACELX) was observed at 1493 cm^{-1} has almost disappeared in its complexes. This indicates the participation of nitrogen atom of azomethine group^{21,22} in coordination. The IR spectra of the complexes show new bands at $490\text{--}495\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $660\text{--}705\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to $\nu(\text{M-N})$ and $\nu(\text{M-O})$ respectively^{23,24}. Also, there is no much difference in the bands at $1670\text{--}1675\text{ cm}^{-1}$, assigned to the carbonyl frequency, indicating its non participation in complexation. The presence of a broad band at 3393 cm^{-1} and 3379 cm^{-1} in the spectra of complexes is associated with coordinated and/or lattice water molecules, as supported from thermal analysis^{25,26} in the complexes. As the IR spectra of complexes were almost similar, the spectra of Cu^{II} complex is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. IR spectrum of salicylidene cephalexin- Cu^{II} complex.

Thermal analysis :

Thermogravimetric analysis shows loss of water molecules in two temperature ranges, depending on whether the water molecule is present as lattice one or a coordinated one. Lattice water molecules are generally eliminated in the temperature range²⁷ of $75\text{--}110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the coordinated water molecules are eliminated at relatively

higher temperatures than those in the case of lattice water molecules²⁸. The results of thermal analysis of the complexes show the elimination of two water molecules in the temperature range of $199\text{--}299\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. This suggests that both the water molecules participate in coordination with the metal ion.

Mass spectra :

The mass spectrum of the Schiff base ligand (Fig. 2) shows a weak molecular ion peak (M^+) peak²⁹ at $m/z = 451$ amu, corresponding to $[\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{S}]^+$. This confirms the proposed molecular formula for Schiff base. The other peaks with m/z values of 424, 406, 345, 328, 317, 277, 231, 210, 192, 154, 136, 124 and 131 amu corresponds to various fragments of Schiff base ligand. Also, the spectra shows that the fragments corresponding to m/z values of 192 is the stablest fragment, the ones at

154, 136, 124, 113 and 210 are less stable while the other fragments are not stable.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectral bands^{30,31} of the free Schiff base of cephalexin studied in methanol exhibited two main peaks. The first absorption band observed at 39215 cm^{-1} (255 nm) for the Schiff base of cephalexin can be as-

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum of the Schiff base.

signed to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition originating in the phenyl ring. This first band was not significantly affected by chelation. The second band in the spectra of Schiff base of cephalosporin at 33333 cm^{-1} (300 nm) may be assigned to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition originating in the azomethine ($\text{CH}=\text{N}$) chromophore. This band undergoes a bathochromic shift to 31746 cm^{-1} (315 nm). This may be attributed to the charge transfer from nitrogen atom of Schiff base ligand to the metal ion ($\text{N} \rightarrow \text{M}$)³². The physical, analytical and spectral study of the Schiff base and its complexes discussed above confirms the coordination of metal to the Schiff base via phenolic deprotonated oxygen and the imino nitrogen³³, thus agreeing well with the proposed structure of SACELEX and its complexes as presented in Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1. Structure of Schiff base.

Scheme 2. Structure of the complex.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Pure sample of cephalosporin monohydrate (molecular formula $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_4\text{S} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$) with mol. wt. 365 was obtained from Lupin Ltd., Bhopal. It was used as such without further purification. Calcium chloride, cobalt nitrate, copper acetate, salicylaldehyde (sal), potassium hydroxide and all other solvents used were of AnalaR grade or Merck products, which were available commercially.

Microanalyses of carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sul-

phur were carried out using Elemental analyzer at Central Drug Research Institute (CDRI), Lucknow. Metal content was determined by Atomic Absorption Spectrometer at Vellore Institute of Technology (VIT), Vellore. IR spectra were recorded on a Spectrum-BX series spectrometer, using KBr discs. Molecular mass was determined by Rast's method. The decomposition temperatures were determined using Gallenkamp melting point apparatus. DTA-DTG-TG was carried out using Perkin-Elmer (Pyris Diamond) analyzer. Mass spectrum was also taken at CDRI, Lucknow.

Synthesis of Schiff base of cephalixin-SACELX :

Methanolic solution of CELX (0.01 M, 25 ml) was added to methanolic solution of salicylaldehyde (0.01 M, 25 ml) and refluxed for three hours. The reaction mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature. On cooling, yellow-orange precipitate was isolated. It was washed with methanol-water (1 : 1) mixture and dried under vacuum. Crystals of SACELX was obtained. UV λ_{\max} (phenyl ring) nm (ϵ) : 250 (40000)–265 (37735); λ_{\max} (-CH=N-) nm (ϵ) : 300 (33333)–350 (28571); FAB-MS m/z : 451 (Calcd. for $C_{23}H_{21}N_3O_5S$: 451); MS m/z : 451 (M^+), 424, 406, 345, 328, 317, 277, 231, 210, 192, 154, 136, 124 and 131 amu.

Synthesis of SACELX- M^{II} complexes :

Methanolic solution of calcium chloride (0.01 M, 25 ml) was added to methanolic solution of SACELX (0.02 M, 25 ml) with constant stirring. The pH was adjusted between 7–8. The mixture was refluxed for 2 to 3 h and cooled to room temperature. On cooling, precipitate was formed, which was filtered, washed with methanol and dried by vacuum suction. Crystals of the Ca^{II} complex was obtained. The procedure was repeated using other metal salts to form their complexes.

Acknowledgement

We thank Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow, Indian Institute of Technology, Roorkee, Vikram University, Ujjain and Meru Research Institute, Bhopal for providing services and facilities required for this work.

References

1. Aurea Echevarria, Maria da Graça Nascimento, Vanilde Geronimo, Joseph Miller and Astréa Giesbrecht, *J. Braz. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **10**, 60.
2. V. E. Kuz'min, V. P. Lozitsky, G. L. Kamalov, R. N. Lozitskaya, A. I. Zheltvay, A. S. Fedtchouk and D. N. Kryzhanovsky, *Acta Biochemical Polonica*, 2000, **47**, 867.
3. Cun-Gen Zhang, Dan Wu, Cheng-Xue Zhao, Jie Sun and Xiang-Fu Kong, *Transition Metal Chemistry*, 1999, **24**, 718.
4. E. Tas, M. Aslanoglu, M. Ulusoy and M. Guler, *Polish J. Chem.*, 2004, **78**, 903.
5. Guangguo Wu, Guoping Wang, Xuchun Fu and Longguan Zhu, *Molecules*, 2003, **8**, 287.
6. Fei Gao, Pin Yang, Jun Xie and Hongfei Wang, *Journal of Inorganic Biochemistry*, 1995, **60**, 61.
7. H. Beraldo and D. Gambinob, *Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*, 2004, **4**, 31.
8. E. Toyota, C. Chinen, H. Sekizaki, K. Itoh and K. Tanizawa, *Chemical and Pharmaceutical Bulletin*, 1996, **44**, 1104.
9. T. Theophanides and J. Anastassopoulou, *Crit. Rev. Oncol. Hematol.*, 2002, **42**, 57.
10. E. J. Margalioth, J. G. Schenker and M. Chevion, *Cancer*, 1983, **52**, 868.
11. J. I. Bullock, M. F. C. Ladd, D. C. Povey and H.-A. Tajmir-Riahi, *Acta Cryst.*, 1979, **B35**, 2013.
12. Mario Sanchez, Melanie J. Harvey, Fredrick Nordstrom, Sean Parkin and David A. Atwood, *Inorganic Chemistry*, 2002, **41**, 5397.
13. H. S. Gold and R. C. Moellering (Jr.), *N. Engl. J. Med.*, 1996, **335**, 1445.
14. J. D. D. Pitout, C. Sanders and W. E. Sanders (Jr.), *Am J. Med.*, 1997, **103**, 51.
15. R. B. Sykes and M. Matthew, *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.*, 1976, **2**, 115.
16. B. Thirumagal, Suman Malik and A. Balasubramaniam, *The Pharmacist*, 2008, **3**, 26.
17. K. Nakamoto, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley Publication, New York, 1970, 103.
18. C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical Applications of IR Spectroscopy", Academic Press, New York, 1963.
19. A. Bavoso, L. Menabue, M. Saladini and M. Sola, *Inorganica Chimica Acta*, 1996, **244**, 207.
20. Fuping Kou, Shourong Zhu, Huakuan Lin, Yunti Chen, Honggen Wang and Xinkai Yao, *Chem. Commun.*, 1996, **59**, 2059.
21. Suchita Singh, Navneet Kaur, S. Varshney and A. K. Varshney, *Research on Chemical Intermediates*, 2004, **30**.
22. Ghassan Ibrahim, Edmond Chebli, A. Mustayeen Khan and M. Gilles Bouet, *Transition Metal Chemistry*, 1999, **24**.
23. A. A. Khandar and K. Nejati, *Polyhedron*, 2000, **19**, 607.

24. K. Rakesh Kohli, K. Gopalakrishnan and P. K. Bhattacharya, *J. Inorg. and Nuclear Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 331.
25. Yanhua Liu, Jiehui Yu, Jingzhe Zhao, Hui Zhang, Yanhui Deng and Zichen Wang, *Thermochimica Acta*, 2004, **419**, 115.
26. M. Olczak-Kobza, *Thermochimica Acta*, 2001, **366**, 129.
27. Z. H. Abdel-Wahab, M. M. Mashaly and A. A. Faheem, *Chem. Pap.*, 2005, **59**, 25.
28. A. Zoya Saveleva, V. Galina Romanenko, A. Liliya Sheludyakova and V. Stanislav Larionov, *Polyhedron*, 2000, **19**, 1737.
29. Williams, "Spectroscopic Methods in Organic Chemistry", Tata McGraw Hill, 1988.
30. Edmond de Hoffman and Vincent Stroobant, "Mass Spectrometry : Principles and Applications". 2nd ed . John Wiley and Sons, 2001.
31. John R. Dyer, "Applications of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd., New Delhi, 1965.
32. B. N. Ghose and K. M. Lasisi, *Synth. Inorg. Metal- Org. Chem.*, 1986, **16**, 1121.